

TAM Questionnaire

Mark your level of agreement with the following statements:

scale 1-7 (1: extremely unlikely/disagree, 7: extremely likely/ agree)

ID	Questionnaire Items
U1	The use of the BlueBot will improve my learning and performance in this subject.
U2	Using BlueBot during classes would make it easier for me to understand certain concepts.
U3	I think the BlueBot is useful when you are learning.
U4	Using the BlueBot would improve my performance.
F1	I think the BlueBot is easy to use.
F2	Learning how to use the BlueBot is not a problem for me.
F3	Learning how to use the BlueBot is clear and understandable.
D1	Using the BlueBot is fun.
D2	I enjoyed using the BlueBot.
D3	I think that the BlueBot allows learning through play.
A1	Using the BlueBot makes learning more interesting.
A2	I got bored while using the BlueBot.
A3	I think that using the BlueBot in the classroom is a good idea.
I1	I would like to use the BlueBot in the future if I have the opportunity.
I2	I would like to use the BlueBot in teaching different subjects.